

THE USE OF FIBERGLASS POSTS FOR THE RESTORATION OF DAMAGED TEETH**Babayev E.,***Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine, assistant***Ashrafov D.,***Department of Orthopedic Dentistry, assistant***Huseynova Çh.***Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine, Assistant**Azerbaijan Medical University**Department of Orthopedic Dentistry**Baku, Azerbaijan*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10082488>**Abstract**

An assessment was made of the quality of restoration of the crowns of pulpless teeth using glass fiber pin constructions from Glassix, which were fixed on a flowable photopolymer composite using various light guides. The length to which the Dentsply liquid SDR filling material polymerizes in the root canal was determined when using modified and conventional light guides for polymerization.

Keywords: fiberglass posts, pulpless teeth, restoration, flowable photopolymer composite material.

One of the most pressing problems of modern dentistry is a reliable restoration of the tooth crown after endodontic treatment. The crown of the tooth can be restored using direct, semi-direct and indirect methods. In dental practice, the direct method of restoring the destroyed crown part of the tooth is more often used. This technique ensures the restoration of lost hard tissues of the tooth in one visit with maximum preservation of its hard tissues. Unlike indirect restoration, this technique contributes to good aesthetic results of restorations and creates a sufficient margin of safety for the restored tooth. When restoring the structure and function of such teeth, it is important to choose the right pin design. Very often metal pins are used, but they have many disadvantages. The main one is excessive pressure on the root, leading to the appearance of cracks and destruction of the tooth. In modern dentistry, fiberglass posts and adhesive techniques are coming to the fore.

Fiberglass is elastic, resilient and bending stronger than metal. The use of fiberglass posts as a root canal filling system has shown high fracture resistance compared to metal posts. Fiberglass posts have a lower modulus of elasticity than dentin, which contributes to the optimal distribution of loads inside the root canal and reduces the possibility of root fracture compared to metal post systems [1]. A rather important component of successful tooth restoration is the correct selection of material for fixing the fiberglass pin in the root canal. The material must have high thixotropic, elastic, elastic and strength properties that meet the biomechanical parameters of hard tooth tissues. Such properties has a fluid photopolymer composite SDR (Dentsply). Also SDR thanks to high volume introduction to 4 mm gives the chance to quickly fill deep cavities. This material gives minimal polymerization shrinkage, which prevents the development of polymerization stress, leading to material detachment, postoperative sensitivity and marginal delamination [2]. The purpose of the study was to evaluate the quality of restoration of the crowns of pulpless teeth using fiberglass pin structures that were fixed on a flowable photopolymer composite,

as well as to determine the length for which the flowable filling material polymerizes in the root canal during polymerization with focus light guides.

Materials and methods

The material for the study was the medial incisors of the upper jaw of male and female people aged 20-45 years, removed due to periodontal tissue disease.

After extraction, the extracted teeth were immediately washed in saline and disinfected in a 6% hydrogen peroxide solution [3]. Trepanation of the crowns of the teeth was performed and access to the root canals was created. The root canals were mechanically processed using reamers to a depth of 6-8 mm, and the pin was adjusted into the root canal. It was then fixed to a flowable composite material. The pinned teeth were cut with a diamond disc in such a way as to obtain halves of the tooth. The inner surfaces of the tooth tissues were polished until a smooth section was obtained. Sections were stained in 1% methylene blue solution with an exposure of 60 min. The obtained samples were studied using binoculars with a magnification of 3.5 times.

The teeth were divided into groups: 1 - control (n=6) - these are teeth restored using fiberglass pins and a fluid composite, the polymerization of which was performed using a standard light guide d=8 mm; 2 - experimental (n=6) - these are teeth restored using fiberglass pins and a fluid composite material, the polymerization of which was performed using a modified funnel-shaped light guide d=3.5 mm, which allows focusing the light into a thin beam. Before fixation in the root canal, fiberglass posts were degreased in 96° alcohol for 3 min, then they were dried and treated with 5th generation PrimeBond NT adhesive (Dentsply) followed by photopolymerization of the adhesive on the post. The surface of the root canal dentin and hard tissues of the crown part of the tooth was treated with 37% phosphoric acid before fixing the fiberglass pin, and the surface of the root canal dentin and hard tissues of the crown part of the tooth was treated with 5th generation adhesive. fiberglass pin in the root canal was fixed to a depth of 6-8 mm, because it is at this length that the

minimum concentration of stress in the tooth and the physiological transfer of the load during eating are observed [4]. Fixation was carried out on a liquid photopolymer material with a photopolymer lamp, the light intensity of which was 500-550 mW/cm², for 30 seconds.

Studying the obtained shaded sections of the teeth, it was found that during polymerization with a photopolymer lamp with a standard light guide, complete staining of the photopolymer with methylene blue is observed in the upper third of the section and uneven staining in the middle third, as evidenced by single intensely colored areas. In the lower third of the section, polymerization did not occur at all. In the second group of samples, where photopolymerization took place using a modified light guide with a diameter of 3.5 mm, we observed uniform photopolymerization in both the upper and middle thirds of the section, as evidenced by its uniform pale blue color, and in the lower third we observed single near-wall areas of intense blue color are placed, which is evidence of an underpolymerized organic matrix of the composite material. Also, 9 patients aged 18-55 years were examined and treated. Using our own method, we restored 9 teeth that were missing a crown. The teeth were restored using the firm's fiberglass posts and flowable composite material. The polymerization of the material in the root canal was performed according to the method used in the extracted teeth.

The operating field was isolated with paper or cotton swabs using a saliva ejector. To prepare the root canal, drills were used at a rotation speed of 200-400 rpm. The quality of the restored tooth crown was assessed immediately after restoration and in the long-term (12 months) period of treatment according to the USPHS criteria, evaluating the anatomical shape, marginal adaptation, surface roughness, marginal coloration, secondary caries, the presence of sensitivity after filling, as well as the state of the contact point. Quality of the contact point checked with floss. If the floss structure was violated, the contact point was considered unsatisfactory. Control examination was carried out in a year. The review paid attention to the anatomical shape, marginal adaptation, marginal coloration, secondary caries, the presence of sensitivity after filling, as well as the state of the contact point. The condition of the restored tooth crowns was conditionally assessed as excellent, satisfactory, unsatisfactory. Excellent (A) restored crown met all criteria. Satisfactory (B) - The restored crown does not meet the ideal score and may need to be

replaced. Unsatisfactory (C) – The restored crown is defective in one of the criteria assessed and should be replaced for prophylactic reasons. Immediately after the restoration of the crown, according to the evaluation criteria (anatomical shape, marginal adaptation, marginal coloration, sensitivity, contact point, the presence of secondary caries), all restored crowns corresponded to the "A" indicator in 100% of cases.

12 months after the examination, 9 patients had no secondary caries. A dense contact point was preserved in 76% of the restored teeth, and in 24% it was not very dense. According to the criterion "marginal adaptation", 8 restored crowns corresponded to the indicator "A", "B" - in one case, "C" was not found. A discoloration between the filling and hard tissues was found in 10.6% of cases. The absence of discoloration was observed in 3 cases. Studies have shown that the restoration of tooth crowns by our method has a number of positive characteristics: correct distribution of the load on the tooth root; very strong and at the same time elastic both as a flowable composite and a fiberglass post that does not change the color of the tooth tissues; the ability to polymerize a flowable composite in the root canal to a depth of 8 mm. The process of fixing the pin is simple and reliable.

The wide application of the proposed method in the clinic for the restoration of dental crowns can significantly reduce the number of complications at minimal economic cost. The teeth restored by the proposed method withstand powerful loads and at the same time the risk of cracks in the root is reduced.

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